

Semi-empirical (PM3) calculations on β -diketones and their Zn^{II} complexes

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Abstract : Semi-empirical calculations on β -diketones (acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane) and their Zn^{II} complexes Zn(acac)₂, Zn(acac)(bzac), Zn(bzac)₂, Zn(acac)(dbzm) and Zn(bzac)(dbzm) have been carried out using PM3 method with the help of MOPAC 6.0 program. The values for the heats of formation, total energies, ionization potentials, atom electron densities, atomic charges, bond lengths and bond angles have been determined and optimized geometries have been worked out. The heats of formation are -117.0306 to -6.3592 kcal, total energies are -4469.3733 to -2602.5726 eV and ionization potentials are 8.9802 to 9.1501 eV. Atom electron densities on the oxygen atoms surrounding zinc atom are 6.2991 to 6.3187 and atomic charges are -0.3187 to -0.2991. Zn-O bond lengths are in the range 1.9796 to 2.0348 Å. O-Zn-O bond angles are close to 109.5° (99.1724° to 122.7135°) supporting distorted tetrahedral geometry for the complexes.

Keywords : Semi-empirical calculations, PM3 method, zinc.

Introduction

PM3 is a semi-empirical method for the quantum calculation of molecular electronic structure in computational chemistry and is based on the Neglect of Differential Diatomic Overlap integral approximation¹. PM3 has a distinct improvement over AM1 and predicts the hypervalent compounds with considerably improved accuracy and overall errors in ΔH_f are reduced by about 40% relative to AM1. Semi-empirical calculations using AM1, PM3 and SAM1 have been reported for acetylacetone and for both the *cis* and *trans* isomers of its 1- and 2- enols. Comparison of the energies of the various species indicates that because of internal H-bonding the cyclic conjugated *cis*-2-enol form is more stable than the cyclic 1-enol². The PM3 calculations have also been carried out for investigating the influence of various internal motions of the enol molecules of acetylacetone on the harmonic vibrational frequencies of the C=O and C=C groups³. Utilizing PM3 method through MOPAC software package in Chem 3D, the first order molecular hyperpolarizabilities of a series of square-pyramidal zinc(II) mixed ligand complexes of the type Zn(acac)₂L (where acac = acetylacetone; L = substituted phenylthioureas : *p*-*N,N'*-dimethylaminophenylthiourea, *p*-methoxyphenylthiourea, *p*-nitrophenylthiourea, *p*-acetylphenylthiourea and *p*-

dimethylaminobenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone) have been evaluated^{4,5}.

Mixed ligand complexes have been implicated in the storage and transport of active substances through membranes. Many inorganic medicinal compounds are mixed ligand complexes and they are also suitable precursors for the selective CVD of high purity metals and have been used in the analysis of semiconductor materials⁶. Synthesis and spectral studies of the mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} of the type ZnLL' (where L = 5-bromo and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and L' = acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane) have been reported earlier from our laboratories^{7,8} and in the present paper the results of semi-empirical calculations on such complexes by PM3 method using MOPAC 2006 software are described.

Methodology :

PM3 calculations for Zn^{II} complexes have been carried out with the help of software MOPAC 6.0. The structures of the complexes are drawn in PH₄ program of Serena software and then notepad file is prepared by giving keywords. This notepad is run in MOPAC software by giving its path and on completion the output file is obtained. This output file contains the data of following parameters :

(i) Heat of formation, (ii) total energies, (iii) ionization potentials, (iv) bond angles, (v) bond lengths, (vi) atom electron densities and (vii) atomic charges.

In the end the structures of the complexes are seen in RASWIN.

Results and discussion

Semi-empirical PM3 calculations have been carried out for Zn^{II} complexes [Zn(acac)₂, Zn(acac)(bzac), Zn(bzac)₂, Zn(acac)(dbzm), Zn(bzac)(dbzm)] (Fig. 2) and various parameters such as heats of formation, total energies, ionization potentials, atom electron densities, atomic charges, bond lengths and bond angles have been calculated.

Fig. 1. Structure of β-diketones.

Fig. 2. Structure of Zn^{II} complexes of β-diketones.

(i) Heats of formation and total energies :

The heat of formation of a molecule is a measure of the internal energy it has. The molecules with a positive heat of formation are less stable energetically than the elements from which they are formed and those with negative heat of formation are more stable.

For Zn^{II} complexes of β-diketones the heats of formation are negative quantities (-117.0306 to -6.3592 kcal, Table 1) and hence they are more stable energetically.

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters for Zn^{II} complexes

Complex	Heat of formation (kcal)	Total energy (eV)	Ionization potential (eV)
Zn(acac)(acac)	-117.0306	-2602.5726	9.1501
Zn(acac)(bzac)	-79.9756	-3224.8324	9.1207
Zn(bzac)(bzac)	-43.3538	-3847.1109	9.0574
Zn(acac)(dbzm)	-40.7095	-3846.9963	8.9867
Zn(bzac)(dbzm)	-6.3592	-4469.3733	8.9802

On the basis of heats of formation, the complexes have following order of stability :

The order of stability can be explained on the basis of +I effect shown by CH₃ group due to which there is a drift of electron density from the carbon atom attached to the CH₃ group towards the oxygen atom as a result of which electron density on oxygen atoms increases giving stronger Zn-O bonds. Hence the complex having more CH₃ groups is expected to be more stable. As the number of bulky groups (e.g. C₆H₅) increases, steric hindrance within the complex increases which affects the stability of the complex. Hence the complex Zn(acac)(acac) is the most stable. In complexes Zn(bzac)(bzac) and Zn(acac)(dbzm), the number of C₆H₅ groups is same but in the former the C₆H₅ groups are far away creating less steric hindrance and hence this complex is slightly more stable as compared to the latter complex. Total energies of Zn^{II} complexes range from -4469.3733 to -2602.5726 eV.

(ii) Ionization potentials :

The ionization potentials of Zn^{II} complexes are in the range 8.9802 to 9.1501 eV. As expected the order of the ionization potential values is same as that for the heats of formation. Ionization potential is the most relevant electronic property for understanding the involvement of electron transfer within the zinc complex and is helpful in understanding the stabilities of the complexes.

(iii) Atom electron densities and atomic charges :

Atom electron densities give an idea about the coordination sites on the ligands through which the metal ions are bound. In the ligands acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane (Fig. 1), the atom electron densi-

ties on the oxygen atoms and carbon atom number 3 are in the range 6.1954 to 6.3930 and 4.3188 to 4.4310 respectively (Table 2a). These data imply that the atom elec-

Ligand	C3	O1	O5
Acetylacetone	4.4310	6.3930	6.2598
Benzoylacetone	4.3188	6.3102	6.2079
Dibenzoylmethane	4.3295	6.3191	6.1954

tron densities on oxygen atoms are greater than those on the carbon atoms which reveals that the metal will coordinate through oxygen not carbon. Most of the elements form stronger bonds with oxygen than with carbon and the resonance stabilization is achieved in oxygen-bonded complexes by the formation of the chelate ring. Hence the oxygen bonded complexes are quite common. However, where the electronegativity of the metal is sufficiently high to reduce the affinity of metal to oxygen, then the C-bonded β -diketones are formed. Atom electron densities on the oxygen atoms surrounding zinc are 6.2991 to 6.3187 (Table 2b), which do not differ significantly from those for the complexes. This may be due to the existence of similar type of ring in ligand due to

Complex	O2	O3	O4	O5
Zn(acac)(acac)	6.3015	6.3006	6.3011	6.3022
Zn(acac)(bzac)	6.3031	6.2998	6.3036	6.2991
Zn(bzac)(bzac)	6.3068	6.3005	6.3001	6.3069
Zn(acac)(dbzm)	6.3039	6.3187	6.3098	6.3043
Zn(bzac)(dbzm)	6.3051	6.3058	6.3010	6.3053

hydrogen bonding. During complex formation hydrogen is merely substituted by the metal ion. Atomic charges on the oxygen atoms surrounding zinc are -0.3187 to -0.2991 (Table 3).

Complex	O2	O3	O4	O5
Zn(acac)(acac)	-0.3238	-0.3006	-0.3011	-0.3022
Zn(acac)(bzac)	-0.3031	-0.2998	-0.3036	-0.2991
Zn(bzac)(bzac)	-0.3068	-0.3005	-0.3001	-0.3069
Zn(acac)(dbzm)	-0.3039	-0.3187	-0.3098	-0.3043
Zn(bzac)(dbzm)	-0.3051	-0.3058	-0.3010	-0.3053

(4) Bond lengths :

Zn-O bond lengths in zinc complexes calculated with the help of PM3 calculations, are in the range 1.9796 to 2.0348 Å (Table 4). These bond lengths are in accord with the X-ray crystal structure data. Zn-O bond distances in Zn(acac)₂.H₂O⁹, Zn(bzac)₂.H₂O¹⁰, Zn(bzac)₂.EtOH¹⁰ and Zn(dpm)₂¹¹ (where dpm = dipivaloylmethane) have been reported to be 1.96, 2.00-2.02, 1.99 and 1.96 Å respectively. O-C bond distances between the oxygen atoms surrounding zinc and the carbon atoms attached to the respective oxygen atoms are in the range 1.2657 to 1.2944 Å (Table 4). The values lie between O-C (1.40 Å) and O=C (1.20 Å) suggesting delocalization of the electrons. These theoretical values are in accord with the X-ray data of Zn(dpm)₂¹¹, in which C-O bond distances have been reported to be 1.274 Å.

(5) Bond angles :

O-Zn-O bond angles are close to 109.5° (99.1724°

Complex	Ligand-I		Ligand-II		Ligand-I		Ligand-II	
	O2-Zn1	O3-Zn1	O4-Zn1	O5-Zn1	C6=O2	C8-O3	C11=O5	C9-O4
Zn(acac)(acac)	2.0013	1.9965	1.9997	1.9958	1.2789	1.2795	1.2800	1.2795
Zn(acac)(bzac)	1.9974	1.9940	1.9994	2.0078	1.2800	1.2810	1.2812	1.2774
Zn(bzac)(bzac)	2.0017	1.9949	1.9957	2.0013	1.2817	1.2797	1.2816	1.2794
Zn(acac)(dbzm)	2.0348	1.9796	2.0126	1.9916	1.2944	1.2657	1.2822	1.2840
Zn(bzac)(dbzm)	1.9989	2.0031	1.9959	1.9981	1.2825	1.2808	1.2801	1.2802

to 122.7135° , Table 5) supporting distorted tetrahedral geometry for the complexes. These bond angles are in accord with the X-ray crystal structure data. The O–Zn–O bond angles in $\text{Zn}(\text{bzac})_2 \cdot \text{EtOH}^{10}$ have been reported to be 103° , 94° and 100° and in $\text{Zn}(\text{dpm})_2^{11}$ 94.7° and 114.2° .

Table 5. Bond angles for Zn^{II} complexes

Complex	O2–Zn–O4	O2–Zn–O5
$\text{Zn}(\text{acac})(\text{acac})$	112.9931	112.7550
$\text{Zn}(\text{acac})(\text{bzac})$	116.4171	115.2258
$\text{Zn}(\text{bzac})(\text{bzac})$	112.7327	113.9873
$\text{Zn}(\text{acac})(\text{dbzm})$	99.1724	122.7135
$\text{Zn}(\text{bzac})(\text{dbzm})$	114.9287	113.0627

The semi-empirical PM3 calculations give various parameters which support the distorted tetrahedral geometry for the complexes. The 3D structures of $\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2$ and $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})(\text{dbzm})]$ complexes are given in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 3. 3D-Structure of $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2]$.

Fig. 4. 3D-Structure of $[\text{Zn}(\text{acac})(\text{dbzm})]$.

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